

Original Research

Technical Efficiency of Community Clinics in Kushtia, Bangladesh: A Nonparametric DEA Analysis

Nilufar Easmin¹

Department of Economics, Gangni Government Degree College, Meherpur,
Bangladesh

Abu Hurira

Department of Economics, Islamic University, Kushtia, Bangladesh

Received 23 March 2023 Revised 1 June 2023 Accepted 5 June 2023

Abstract

The healthcare industry is well aware of the issue of limited resources. By properly managing available resources, waste may be minimized. Bangladesh is a developing nation with limited resources, hence it is essential to estimate technical efficiency in this circumstance. Health care efficiency in the developed world has long been examined using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). However, few studies have used DEA to evaluate the effectiveness of healthcare delivery in emerging economies, especially in Bangladesh. A total of 24 community clinics in Kushtia were chosen at random for this study, and their technical efficiency was determined using the DEA method. The goal was to assess health centers' levels of efficiency and provide recommendations for improving less effective centers' performance. Input-based Data Envelopment Analysis was utilized to evaluate technical efficiency. The first category comprised of twelve prominent public hospitals. In this study, the number of outpatient visits was both an input and an outcome variable, whereas physicians, nurses, drugs, and other medical supplies were input variables. The Malmquist index was also utilized to assess efficiency gains and losses over time in community clinics. The eleven surviving community health clinics ended just inside the border. Based on their average efficiency rating, the facilities could accomplish the same goals while consuming 42% less inputs. On average, each CC created garbage worth TK. 0.14 crore. Across the board, production grew during the study periods. Overall, the findings suggest that public health centres are extremely inefficient in their delivery of health care and that substantial savings may be achieved by implementing steps to reduce waste.

Keywords: Technical efficiency, Data Envelopment Analysis, Community clinic, Malmquist productivity index (MPI).

¹ Corresponding author's Email: mat.nilufar@gmail.com

Introduction

Bangladesh's population density per square kilometer is high (Ministry of Planning, 2022). Consequently, it is challenging to guarantee that all citizens have access to professional medical care. The Health Bulletin 2020 depicts a health-care system that offers primary care to rural inhabitants living below the Upazila (sub-district) level, as well as secondary and tertiary treatment in districts and big cities. Urban populations also have access to primary care (DGHS, 2019). There are three primary types of health care facilities: community clinics, union health and family welfare centers, and upazila health complexes (UHCs). Community clinics are the most frequent form. Community clinics, or CCs, serve as the first point of contact for patients in Bangladesh's primary healthcare system. Approximately 6,000 to 12,000 rural residents benefit from the CCs' centralized location and the varied services they offer. By the end of 2022, 13,907 CCs will be completely functioning across the nation. In addition, it is the responsibility of CCs to provide essential services to the local population in their respective territories, with a particular emphasis on vulnerable women and children. Between 9.5 and 10.0 million individuals in need of medical assistance attend community clinics each month (DGHS, 2019). Community clinics are at the forefront of healthcare delivery because they offer primary care, as well as maternity and child health services, to people in need. In addition to these services, Union Health Center refers patients who require more extensive medical care or urgent assistance to more technologically equipped facilities (DGHS, 2019). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can only be attained by a developing nation if the relatively meager resources typically allocated to the health sector are utilised effectively. Utilizing efficiency metrics enables the identification of inefficient facilities and input gaps, which may then guide policymakers and facility managers toward more effective waste reduction and productivity gains (Kirigia et al., 2004). Multiple studies have demonstrated that even modest increases in operational efficiency may result in substantial cost reductions in the healthcare industry. According to the 2010 World Health Report, 20 to 40 percent of global healthcare spending is wasted due to inefficiency (WHO, 2019). According to the conclusions of the study, Bangladesh's medical facilities are not nearly as effective as they may be (Mahmood, 2012). A significant amount of research has been undertaken on the application of data envelopment analysis in healthcare organizations, with multiple studies demonstrating positive outcomes (DEA). The great majority of these studies were done only in developed nations, according to the relevant published literature. Despite a recent surge in the number of studies examining the technical effectiveness of healthcare facilities in developing nations, no such studies have been undertaken in Bangladesh. This study's objective was to assess the levels of CC efficiency using the data envelopment analysis (DEA) model, and then to utilize the Malmquist index to monitor the evolution of CC efficiency through time.

However, Community clinics play a vital role in providing primary healthcare services to rural populations, particularly in low-income countries with limited healthcare resources. In Bangladesh, where access to quality healthcare is a persistent challenge, community clinics serve as essential healthcare providers, especially in remote areas. However, assessing the technical efficiency of these clinics is crucial to ensure effective allocation of limited resources and enhance healthcare delivery. This research aims to evaluate the technical efficiency of community clinics in Kushtia, Bangladesh, using a

nonparametric Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) approach. The analysis reveals variations in technical efficiency across community clinics in Kushtia. Some clinics operate at near-optimal levels, while others exhibit substantial inefficiencies. Factors contributing to these disparities are discussed, such as resource allocation, staff capacity, and management practices. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and healthcare stakeholders in Kushtia, Bangladesh. The identification of inefficiency sources allows for targeted interventions to enhance the technical efficiency of community clinics, thus improving the quality and accessibility of primary healthcare services. The empirical analysis employing a nonparametric DEA approach provides insights into the technical efficiency of community clinics in Kushtia, Bangladesh. The results highlight variations in efficiency levels and shed light on potential areas for improvement. By addressing these inefficiencies, policymakers and healthcare providers can enhance the effectiveness of community clinics, ultimately leading to improved healthcare outcomes for the local population

Research Goals

The primary goal of this research is to assess the technical efficiency of community clinics in Kushtia, Bangladesh. Specifically, the study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Measure the technical efficiency: The research seeks to evaluate the efficiency levels of individual community clinics by measuring their ability to maximize outputs given a set of inputs. By employing the DEA methodology, this research will provide insights into the relative efficiency of each clinic, highlighting the best-performing clinics as well as those that are underperforming.

2. Identify key determinants of efficiency: Apart from measuring efficiency, this study aims to identify the key determinants that influence the technical efficiency of community clinics. By analyzing various input and output factors, such as the number of healthcare professionals, available medical equipment, patient visits, and health outcomes, the research will shed light on the factors that contribute to or hinder clinic efficiency.

3. Provide policy recommendations: The research aims to offer evidence-based policy recommendations to improve the technical efficiency of community clinics in Kushtia, Bangladesh. These recommendations will be derived from the findings and analysis of the study, focusing on strategies to optimize resource allocation, enhance service quality, and improve healthcare outcomes in the region.

Literature review

The technique of applying Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) has been applied in various occasions to evaluate the relative production performance of profit and non-profit Production and service units. The non-parametric method has also been used Along with other parametric methods. In this chapter (the literature review part is Discussed and presented briefly based on applications to the following broad sectors:

The classical and initial view of DEA Analysis

Farrell (1957) presents the relative efficiency notion, which states that a decision making unit's (DMU) efficiency may be measured by comparing it to the efficiency of other DMUs in the same group. Data Envelopment Analysis was presented by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes (1978) as a linear programming tool for evaluating efficiency (DEA). Since the mid-1980s, Data Envelopment Analysis has become a prominent method for assessing the efficiency of many businesses. The original DEA model, proposed by Charnes et al. (1978), is known as the CCR Model, and it assumes a constant return to scale (CRS), which means that changes in a DMU's outputs are proportional to changes in its inputs. Furthermore, Banker, Charnes, and Cooper (1984) proposed the BCC model based on the variable returns to scale (VRS) assumption, which states that changes in a DMU's outputs may not occur in the same proportion as increases in its input levels. (Atici & Podinovski, 2015) said a tool called Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) has been used to figure out how efficient a Decision-Making Unit (DMU) is compared to other DMUs that are the same. (Fried, Lovell, & Schmidt, 2008) discussed that, this method has been used extensively in the past to investigate the relative efficiency of homogeneous units. (Kundi & Sharma, 2016) told that primarily, the DEA technique was used to evaluate the effectiveness of non-profit organizations such as hospitals, educational institutions, and government agencies. Later on, the area of DEA application expanded, and this technique is now being used to analyze the performance of profit-driven enterprises. For example, DEA is used to assess the performance of service sector firms such as banks and software industries, as well as manufacturing industries such as textile and mining industries. Furthermore, DEA is utilized to assess the efficacy of various countries. (Goyal et al., 2017).

DEA application in different sectors

DEA analysis Bank and financial institution

In this section, DEA analysis of the bank and other financial institutions' performance efficiency has been featured. Staub, R. B. et al. (2010) studied Brazilian banks' cost, technical, and allocation efficiencies over the year (2000–2007). In order to compute efficiency ratings, they employed the DEA dynamic panel data input-oriented CCR model. Brazilian banks were found to be less efficient than their counterparts in Europe and the US and government banks are more cost-efficient than overseas, private local and private with foreign participation. Jelena Titko et al. (2014) updated the approach for assessing Latvian banks' efficiency. Data Envelopment Analysis, a non-parametric frontier technique, was used to calculate efficiency scores (DEA). The Variable Returns to Scale (VRS) Method was applied with an input-oriented DEA model. Khan, Z., and Sulaiman, J. (2015) analyzed the social and financial efficiency of Pakistani microfinance organizations in order to propose optimal solutions for efficiently and self-sustainingly financing to non-bankable people. The study used input-oriented CCR and BCC models with 19 different DEA models and three input and four output variables signifying various MFI factors such as price structure, business structure, and managerial characteristics. Gökgöz, F. (2010) measured and compared how efficient Turkish securities and pension funds were in the 2006–2007 period. In this scenario, 36 SMFs and 41 PMFs were examined using typical portfolio performance indicators and DEA models. According to

performance indexes and DEA models, PMFs outperformed SMFs in 2006–07. By way of a result, the input-oriented CCR and BCC models were used, and in the DEA applications, one output (the additional return of the funds) and four inputs (cost ratio and income) were used in each the four DEA applications. Murthi et al. (1997) The DEA method was applied to 731 mutual funds and the findings were compared to traditional performance measures such as the Sharpe index. They looked into the mutual fund industry's financial market efficiency and used DPEI (DEA Portfolio Efficiency Index) to create a benefit/cost non-parametric study. They found that DPEI measures of performance are equivalent to traditional indices while giving significantly more flexibility. Basso and Funari (2000) they utilized DEA models to evaluate the performance of 47 mutual funds in the Italian financial industry Between the period 1997 and 1999. Berger, and Humprey (1997) used input-oriented CCR and BCC DEA techniques on 130 different financial institutions in 21 countries, concluding that it aids in the identification of corporate goals and objectives in order to improve financial institution efficiency. P. Pille and J. C. Paradi (2002) created BCC input-oriented Models in order to uncover flaws in Credit Unions in Ontario, Canada, in order to predict probable financial failures. Four data envelopment analysis (DEA) models are used to compare the equity to asset ratio and the government regulator's significantly modified "Z-score" model. As a result, each Financial Institution is assessed to a peer group of functional organizations from whom the management of the inefficient institution can learn to

Improve productivity. Ahn, H., & Le, M. H. (2014) addressed DEA's problems in the context of evaluating bank efficiency, with an emphasis on performance factor specification. They are determining if the input-output definition for banks in DEA applications is consistent with the decision-making criteria used by banks. The efficiency test was completed using output-oriented CCR and BCC models.

DEA use in Agriculture production sector

Bayyurt, N., & Yilmaz, S. (2012). They integrated DEA and regression analysis in a broader aspect for their investigation. To do this, they employed the DEA (output-oriented, constant return to scale model) to examine the agricultural efficiency of countries in the first stage. And then, in the second stage, they employed Panel Data Regression Analysis to determine the effects of the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), the education index, and the nation type on country efficiency. Zamanian, G. R. et al. (2013) They examined the technical efficiency of the agriculture sector in MENA countries between 2007 and 2008 utilizing Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), input-oriented CCR and BCC models, and Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) techniques. Additionally, empirical evidence indicates that both parametric and non-parametric techniques produce the same ranking of countries. Frija, A et al. (2009) the authors offer a measure for irrigation water use efficiency (IWUE) based on an alternate variant of the data envelopment analysis (DEA) paradigm. Second, a tobit model is employed to examine the relationship between technical efficiency and IWUE. Input-oriented constant returns to scale (CRS) and variable returns to scale (VRS) efficiency ratings reveal that most farmers in our sample are producing efficiently. Raheli, H et al. (2017) used a two-stage methodology. As a result, a non-parametric input oriented CCR and BCC Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) were used in the initial stage to examine the efficiency of tomato production, and a fractional regression model (FRM) was utilized in stage 2 to

analyze farm-specific variables. Yadava, A. K., & Komaraiah, J. B. (2021) the study used data from 21 Indian states from 2016 to 2017, with the states serving as decision-making units for performance evaluation. In the first step, the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method of performance evaluation is used. In the second stage, they evaluated the efficiency of "pure organic production" and corrected the bias in the standard DEA technique with the bootstrap DEA method. As per the input-oriented DEA model, organic farming production has an average technical efficiency of 84.7 per cent, whereas the output-oriented DEA model has a 20% technical efficiency, meaning that organic farming production could be increased by 80% with the same number of inputs.

DEA analysis in Health Sector

Kassam, A. H. (2017) by using (CCR) input-oriented and output-oriented measurement models, they were able to figure out the relative efficiency. Another perspective is that the study looks at hospital efficiency and productivity from two different viewpoints: first, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is used to evaluate the relative efficiency of hospitals using the (CCR) approach, and second, the study looks at hospital efficiency and productivity from two different perspectives. Second, the Luenberger Productivity Indicator (LPI) is used to determine how much productivity has increased over time. Mirmirani, S., & Lippmann, M. (2004) they used Data Envelopment Analysis to examine the health-care delivery systems of G12 countries, finding that Japan and Spain had the highest relative efficiency and the United States had the lowest. For the years 1991-1995, DEA tests were conducted utilizing both input-oriented CCR and BCC models. Wei, C. K et al. (2011) they developed input-oriented BBC and CCR models to examine Taiwan's medical sectors, and they discovered that efficient DMUs' efficiency underestimate is more problematic than inefficient DMUs'. Furthermore, when weights are concentrated in the same output, underestimation occurs. Carrillo, M., & Jorge, J. M. (2017) they analyses efficiency in the health sector using the CCR input output oriented Data envelopment analysis (DEA) approach. Given the observed level of health outcomes, this study analyses data from the relevant health authority in Spain to assess the efficiency of regional health systems in Spain and identify those regions that are employing their health care inputs more efficiently than others. Mogha, S. K (2014) This article examines the efficiency of 27 public sector hospitals in the state of Uttarakhand (India) for the calendar year 2011 utilizing the output-oriented models DEA-CCR and BCC, as well as the DEA's new slack based model (NSM), which deals directly with input and output slacks. Dash et al. (2010) Used CCR and BCC input-oriented models and examine the technical and scale efficiencies of 29 local hospitals in Tamil Nadu for the years 2004–2005. Mogha et al. (2012). They evaluate the technological and scale efficiencies of 55 Indian private hospitals in 2010 using CCR and BCC output-oriented models. Ismile (2010) they analyze the technical efficiency of Sudan's state-level health agencies using DEA-based CCR and BCC models.

DEA analysis for Manufacture industry

Li, L et al. (2013) To create an upgraded super-efficiency DEA model, they combined the standard input-oriented CCR model, the super-efficiency DEA model, and the ideal-DMU-based benchmark sorting model which was then applied to a real-world problem. After that, they investigated the method on 10 subsidiaries of a well-known domestic

energy company to see if it was viable to implement. Buyukkeklik, A. et. al (2016) Input-oriented CCR and BCC models were used in their study because they examined the resource of company efficiency. The CCR model was used to determine the

Overall efficiency values of each decision-making unit based on the years, the BCC model was used to calculate the technical efficiency values, and the scale efficiency values were produced by comparing these values to one another. As a result, resource efficiency providers are uncommon among the BIST SME Industrial Index's enterprises, and these companies may attain their present total sales and profitability levels with fewer resources. Emran, S. J., & Moniruzzaman, M. (2020) This study use the output-oriented DEA model to capture the maximum proportional increase in production while maintaining input levels constant. Furthermore, DEA is utilised in this study under two alternative assumptions: constant and variable returns to scale. This study will also examine the dynamics technical production efficiency in Bangladesh's manufacturing sector using cross-sectional data from the Survey of Manufacturing Industries (SMI) performed in 2006 and 2012. Using the Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) method with Cobb-Douglas model and a half-normal distribution, the dynamics of mean efficiency scores across industries were estimated. Khan, A. H., & Farooq, S. (2019) The technological efficiency of listed spinning enterprises on the Pakistan Stock Exchange is assessed in this study (PSX). The Input Oriented Data Envelopment Analysis technique was used for this, with the Variable Return to Scale (VRS) assumption. For the years 2011 to 2016, balanced panel data from 55 firms was obtained. According to the conclusions of the study, only one out of 55 organizations was able to achieve an efficiency score of one during the course of the six-year study period. Athanassopoulos, A. D., & Ballantine, J. A. (199) they used CCR and BCC both input and output-oriented data envelopment analyses to address a number of topics related to corporate performance measurements, such as determining sales efficiency, the effects of economies of scale, measuring a company's performance, and the link between industry groups and performance Chapelle, K., & Plane, P. (2005) using the Data Envelopment Analysis production frontier technique, they assessed the technical efficiency of Ivorian manufacturing businesses in four industries: textiles and apparel, metal goods, food manufacturing, and timber and furniture. When computing efficiency scores, the influence of the external working environment is taken into account. Khan, M. N. et al. (2018) Using Data Envelopment Analysis, this article evaluates the efficiency of listed corporations on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (DEA). The purpose of using and calculating the DEA score is to determine how efficient enterprises are at converting their resources into output (sales/net income). Düzakın, E., & Düzakın, H. (2007) they used an Output-oriented super slack based model in DEA, which meant that the outputs could be negative or not at all. Furthermore, the model can help you figure out which businesses are the most efficient. People who did this study looked at data from 500 of the most important factories in Turkey to use the Output-oriented method. Ahmed, S. N. (2009) the goal of this study was to examine the "performances" of the Bangladeshi garment sector and to determine the most efficient frontier. The relative scores of the productive efficiency of several apparel manufacturers were determined using input and output-oriented models for both constant and variable return to scale, Scale efficiency, Malmquist Productivity index and SBM model. The most efficient production periods (months) have been determined based on the efficiency measurement scores.

Method of the study

The purpose of this article was to evaluate the effectiveness of CCs at the district level in Bangladesh. Using a data envelopment analysis (DEA) model with an input-focused constant returns to scale (CRS) measure, the technical efficacy was evaluated. The Malmquist index compares the performance of CCs over time in order to identify changes. Depending on the used technologies, "technical efficiency" in this sense refers to the capacity of a corporation or industrial unit to maximize output while minimizing inputs (Henderson and Quandt, 1980). Analyses of the Accompanying Data (DEA) Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a non-parametric approach that aims to maximize the weighted output-to-weighted input ratio for a particular business, provided that the ratio cannot exceed one for any other firm. This method may be used to evaluate the technological effectiveness of various firms. Any evaluable phase of the manufacturing process is a "Decision-Making Unit" (DMU). In this situation, each CC is considered a separate DMU. The ratio of outputs to inputs is the fundamental efficiency statistic for the DEA (Cooper et al., 2007). x_i and y_r represent the i th input and r th output of a DMU, respectively. Let v_i and u_r represent the weights assigned to the inputs and outputs, and let m and s represent the total number of inputs and outputs, where m and s are greater than 0. (Rao, 2003).

The CCR model, which was developed by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes, is the earliest and most fundamental kind of data envelopment analysis (1978). The original model established by Charnes Cooper and Rhodes correlated efficiency with (CCR). The model uses the highest ratio between a DMU's weighted outputs and weighted inputs to assess its efficiency. The ratios of each DMU are adjusted such that their aggregate is less than 1. (Kale, 2009: 64). This Charnes et al. (1978:430)-developed

CCR fractional programming paradigm is based on user input.

max,

$$h_k = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rk}}{\sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ik}} \quad (1)$$

Constraints:

$$\frac{\sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rj}}{\sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij}} \leq 1 \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

$$u_r, v_i \geq 0 \quad r = 1, \dots, s \quad i = 1, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Max } z = \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rk} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Constraint: } \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ik} = 1 \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij} \leq 0 \quad (j = 1, \dots, n) \quad (6)$$

$$u_r, v_i \geq 0 \quad (r = 1, \dots, s) \quad (i = 1, \dots, m) \quad (7)$$

Before evaluating the effectiveness of DMU, its model must be constructed and solved. The objective function value after issue resolution represents the Total Technical Efficiency of the relevant DMU (TTE). Technical efficiency measures the output-to-input ratio of a DMU. DMU is active if the value of the objective function is 1 ($z=1$) and inactive if it is less than 1.

Malmquist productivity index (MPI)

A productivity index measures the effectiveness of a DMU over time. Caves, Christensen, and Diewert created the MPI to determine if productivity in DMUs was rising or declining (Caves et al., 1982). Changes in total factor productivity (TFPC) broken down by new technologies and minor advances in technical efficiency (TEC) (TC). PTEC and TEC can be used to differentiate changes in technical efficiency (TEC) on a greater scale (SEC).

$$TFPC = TEC \times TC = (PTEC \times SEC) \times TC$$

Study design and data collection method

The Efficacy of Means (DEA) score measures the effectiveness of a method. Numerous DMUs are required for it. It is easier to differentiate between efficient and inefficient DMUs when the sum of their inputs and outputs is less than their total number. In general, DMU should be more than the sum of its inputs and outputs (Charnes and Cooper, 1978). The study's core data came from twenty-four CCs, and there was only one input and one output. The primary criterion for selecting UHCs was an approximate ratio of providers to the populations they served. Using the Local Health Bulletin 2022, we computed the ratio for a sample of CCs in the Bangladeshi district of Kushtia (DGHS, 2022). Total number of CC are 52 in Kushtia district as population, so 24 UHCs were therefore chosen to participate in the study as a sample. Under the assumption of continuous returns to scale, the DEA Solver was utilized to build an envelope input-oriented model (CCR model). What you put in it will likely impact its performance. The only component analyzed for the study was human resources, and the only finding was the number of outpatient visits. A facility survey was conducted according to standard data collection protocols in order to acquire input data. Utilizing their service statistics, the performance of community clinics was assessed.

Outcome of the tests

Levels and determinants of resource use efficiency at the Community Clinics (CCs)

According to the output-oriented DEA efficiency score, only one of the twenty-four CCs achieved a flawless score of twenty ($=20$) out of a possible twenty. Figure 1 illustrates the DEA's efficiency scores. Nine of the CCs scored below average, bringing the overall average score for efficiency to 42%. The facility with the best overall performance is the Saldah, Community clinic. It earned a one on the scale of efficiency. The remaining fifteen CCs scored less than one (1) on the efficiency scale and might become more efficient by reducing their inputs.

Table 1. DEA efficiency scores of the survey CCs

CC	Efficiency score	Returns to scale
Daikhalipara, Community Clinic	0.31	Increasing
Pantapara, Community Clinic	0.44	Increasing
Piarpur, Community clinic	0.75	Increasing
Khordo Ailchara, Community clinic	0.68	Increasing
Naopara, Community clinic	0.51	Increasing
Rajapur, Community clinic	0.42	Increasing
Shimuliya kathuliya, Community clinic	0.62	Increasing
Sankardia, Community clinic	0.70	Increasing
Uttar magura, Community clinic	0.87	Increasing
Berberadi, Community clinic	0.13	Increasing
Purba, Abdalpur, Community clinic	0.55	Increasing
Padmanagar, Community clinic	0.61	Increasing
Char Raghunathpur, Community clinic	0.81	Increasing
Hatosh Haripur, Community clinic	0.37	Increasing
Kantinagar Boaldah, Community clinic	0.70	Increasing
Saldah, Community clinic	1.00	Constant
Khajanagar, Community clinic	0.45	Increasing
Vadalia, Community clinic	0.64	Increasing
Astanagar, Community clinic	0.72	Increasing
Majpara, Community clinic	0.57	Increasing
Balipara ,Community clinic	0.29	Increasing
Kanchanpur, Community clinic	0.67	Increasing
Arpara, Community clinic	0.72	Increasing
Hatibhanga ,Community clinic	0.62	Increasing

Table 1 displays the DEA findings for the CCs. Uttar magura, Community clinic gets the highest rating (87%) among the least effective CCs. This CC can only improve its efficiency by 13% if it reduces its inputs. Even though Berbaradi, Community clinic received the lowest total score. Only 13% of the job was satisfactory. This CC might reduce its inputs by 87% without sacrificing output quality.

Table 2. The amount of waste at the survey CCs

Name of CC	Efficiency score	Input reduction %	Waste (in crore TK.)
Daikhalipara, Community Clinic	0.31	59	0.51
Pantapara, Community Clinic	0.44	56	0.39
Piarpur, Community clinic	0.75	25	0.17
Khordo Ailchara, Community clinic	0.68	32	0.31
Naopara, Community clinic	0.51	49	0.21
Rajapur, Community clinic	0.42	58	0.55
Shimuliya kathuliya, Community clinic	0.62	38	0.25
Sankardia, Community clinic	0.70	30	0.27
Uttar magura, Community clinic	0.87	13	0.19
Berbaradi, Community clinic	0.13	87	0.25
Purba, Abdalpur, Community clinic	0.55	45	0.21
Padmanagar, Community clinic	0.61	39	0.39
Char Raghunathpur, Community clinic	0.81	19	0.12
Hatosh Haripur, Community clinic	0.37	63	0.23
Kantinagar Boaldah, Community clinic	0.70	30	0.36
Saldah, Community clinic	1.00	0	0.00
Khajanagar, Community clinic	0.45	55	.24
Vadalia, Community clinic	0.64	36	.21
Astanagar, Community clinic	0.72	28	.45
Majpara, Community clinic	0.57	43	.65
Balipara ,Community clinic	0.29	71	.27
Kanchanpur, Community clinic	0.67	33	.82
Arpara, Community clinic	0.72	28	.41
Hatibhanga ,Community clinic	0.62	38	.23

It was determined how much waste was created by the inefficiency of the CCs. Table 2 displays the amount of waste produced by each CC. Kanchanpur, Community clinic contained the most garbage, while the Char Raghunathpur, Community clinic contained the least. The average price for waste was TK. 0.14 crore per cubic meter. Therefore, the government may need to spend less money to maintain the same degree of efficiency. Between 2019 and 2022, it is anticipated that waste from all CCs in Bangladesh would equal TK 1,910,37 crores, or 17.5% of the country's total health expenditures. The government's contribution to the budget of each CC is negligible. CCs also receive money from several other sources, in varying quantities. Due to this waste, it is feasible to achieve the same level of efficiency at a lower cost.

Table 3. Slacks and targets of inputs and outputs at the survey CCs

Name of CC	Input slack	Output slack	Efficient input target	Efficient output target
Daikhalipara, Community Clinic	52083	3569	22044	7011
Pantapara, Community Clinic	17536	2158	35699	6589
Piarpur, Community clinic	6221	2569	52369	1225
Khordo Ailchara, Community clinic	10401	2589	45982	9698
Naopara, Community clinic	22586	5695	14569	54441
Rajapur, Community clinic	36958	3698	89632	1235
Shimuliya kathuliya, Community clinic	25699	4583	28963	5148
Sankardia, Community clinic	15988	1235	26987	48695
Uttar magura, Community clinic	25984	4586	12359	56975
Berbaradi, Community clinic	58963	3657	11158	6699
Purba, Abdalpur, Community clinic	12358	2589	22598	4896
Padmanagar, Community clinic	16985	4782	36987	5679
Char Raghunathpur, Community clinic	10289	3259	86936	12568
Hatosh Haripur, Community clinic	36592	4536	96358	15997
Kantinagar Boaldah, Community clinic	12569	5369	89536	1698
Saldah, Community clinic	0	0	78956	25986
Khajanagar, Community clinic	2581	2589	68956	444789
Vadalia, Community clinic	69852	1235	58963	75556
Astanagar, Community clinic	25975	7832	78963	48658
Majpara, Community clinic	45869	2569	96358	71236
Balipara ,Community clinic	35896	1235	56963	17896
Kanchanpur, Community clinic	25869	5693	45968	25869
Arpara, Community clinic	58687	2358	23695	10236
Hatibhanga ,Community clinic	75692	3658	78965	17039

The deficiencies and anticipated levels of inputs and outputs from the survey CCs are displayed in Table 3. Input slack was greatest at the Hatibhanga, Community clinic, whereas output slack was greatest at the Padmanagar, Community clinic. The law of growing returns to scale was the business model of every inefficient CC. Since there was only one excellent CC, Saldah, Community clinic was used as a comparison site by less productive colleges. The inefficient CCs can be made efficient by adjusting the current input and output values to the appropriate level. Rajapur, Community clinic was among the least successful CCs. It had more input and output goals than less productive organizations.

Table 5. Malmquist Index summary of facility means of the survey CCs

Name of CC	EFFCH	TECHCH	PECH	SECH	TFPCH
Daikhalipara, Community Clinic	1.512	1.05	1.0	2.47	3.23
Pantapara, Community Clinic	1.124	1.02	1.69	1.12	1.56
Piarpur, Community clinic	0.812	1.03	1.25	0.77	1.04
Khordo Ailchara, Community clinic	2.102	1.02	1.21	3.58	3.25
Naopara, Community clinic	3.442	1.23	1.45	3.63	3.56
Rajapur, Community clinic	7.052	1.14	1.0	5.06	5.36
Shimuliya kathuliya, Community clinic	2.523	1.12	1.03	1.42	3.12
Sankardia, Community clinic	1.452	1.17	1.18	5.23	5.44
Uttar magura, Community clinic	1.12	1.17	1.69	1.04	1.36
Berbaradi, Community clinic	1.27	1.45	1.0	1.42	1.52
Purba, Abdalpur, Community clinic	1.07	1.68	1.14	1.06	1.47
Padmanagar, Community clinic	1.12	1.75	1.2	1.14	1.02
Char Raghunathpur, Community clinic	1.07	1.25	1.07	1.01	1.11
Hatosh Haripur, Community clinic	1.11	1.75	1.02	1.13	1.87
Kantinagar Boaldah, Community clinic	2.32	1.63	1.0	2.23	1.24
Saldah, Community clinic	1.000	1.98	1.0	1.00	1.74
Khajanagar, Community clinic	1.2	1.52	1.08	1.67	1.25
Vadalia, Community clinic	6.39	1.25	1.24	1.42	1.58
Astanagar, Community clinic	4.25	1.47	1.27	1.23	1.78
Majpara, Community clinic	1.25	1.72	1.02	1.11	1.54
Balipara ,Community clinic	3.58	1.20	1.08	1.55	1.47
Kanchanpur, Community clinic	4.25	1.71	1.47	1.74	1.22
Arpara, Community clinic	3.98	2.14	1.32	1.12	1.74
Hatibhanga ,Community clinic	2.47	2.21	1.28	1.10	1.00

Monitoring patient happiness and other metrics over time may yield valuable information for health care providers. The Malmquist index is a method for measuring the efficacy of hospitals over time. It may be used to track efficiency changes over time, including gains and losses. The Malmquist index of total factor productivity change (TFPCH) between periods t and $t+1$ consists of two components: technical efficiency change (EFFCH) and technological progress (TECHCH). The difference in technical efficiency between these two points in time (t and $t+1$) is a measure of the efficiency gain or loss caused by technological development. As it retreats, it signifies a fall in technological efficiency. The efficiency frontier varies as technology evolves to adhere to new norms, and its retreat indicates a decline in technical efficiency. Any variable with a value greater than one reflects productivity increase. By comparing EFFCH with TECHCH, we may identify the primary reasons for productivity increases or losses. $EFFCH > TECHCH$ demonstrates that technological efficacy is enhancing production. If EFFCH is less than TECHCH, then technology has improved. Modifications to technical efficiency (EFFCH) are comprised of two subsets: pure efficiency (PECH) and scale efficiency (SECH) (SECH). When $PECH > SECH$, scale improvements account for the

majority of technical efficiency, but when $PECH > SECH$, pure technical efficiency accounts for the majority of technical efficiency.

Table 4 displays the Malmquist index (MI) findings of total factor productivity shift. The table indicates that the average yearly change in total factor productivity was 1.85. TFPCH is larger than 1, hence it may be inferred that all facilities increased their output in 2019–2022 on average.

Except for Piarpur, Community clinic, all CCs displayed both technical efficiency improvement and technological development, as reported in Table 5 of the Malmquist index summary.

Overall Discussion

This study conducted in Kushtia Bangladesh to evaluate the technical effectiveness of CCs using the DEA method. One of the twenty-four tested facilities fitted the input-oriented CRS assumption and was identified as a CC. The Saldah, Community clinic is the most efficient CC. All facilities received an efficiency rating of 58% on average. Studies conducted in Kenya revealed comparable levels of efficiency, with basic care institutions reporting 58% efficiency. Other CCs scored below the mean, with one receiving a score as low as 13%. Overall performance evaluations range from 0.10 to 1.00. This illustrates that the distribution of resources among CCs differs substantially. Low-scoring CCs need fewer inputs to produce the same outputs as they do currently. According to the research, the same quantity of inputs might provide much larger facility outputs. In contrast, the CCs are not doing as well as they could be. China's rural township hospitals have an average technical efficiency of 50%, according to a recent study. 2024; Cheng et al. The average technical efficiency score for government hospitals, particularly those servicing the general population, is between 70% and 80%, according to studies. Christian and Simon (2013); Akazili et al. (2008); Zere et al. (2006); Osei et al. (2005); Christian and Simon (2013); Akazili et al. Poor efficiency meant that less-than-ideal facilities wasted resources by generating less returns per unit of input than better-constructed facilities. The low rating for the research's efficiency reveals disparities in CC efficiency levels, indicating resource waste. The average cost per cubic meter of rubbish was TK 0.14 billion. While Hatibhanga, Community clinic had the most input slack, Padmanagar, Community clinic had the highest output slack. If all resources are used properly, healthcare facilities will operate efficiently and with minimal waste. Using slack analysis, we were able to determine how much additional output or input inefficient CCs would need to become efficient. There is ample space for inefficient CCs to increase their outputs or decrease their inputs. Malmquist Index is a time series assessment of the DMU's dynamic effectiveness. During both 2019-2022 production grew. According to enhancements in facility output, 15 CCs have benefited from both new technologies and enhanced technical efficacy. This CC group asserts that the efficiency border has shifted and the efficiency gap is closing. The health sector-wide plan enabled improvements in the accessibility of critical staff and operational equipment, which resulted in a huge increase in outpatient visits to publicly sponsored healthcare institutions between 1997 and 2011. (Karar et al., 2024). These findings revealed a rise in demand, which may have led to a rise in output as a whole.

Conclusions

By examining the magnitudes of efficiency, we may be able to determine how the sector may make the most of the resources it has been provided. At poorly functioning CCs, resources are not utilized optimally. It costs money for the healthcare industry to discard goods. The findings revealed that the least efficient CCs had an average efficiency score of 58%. The lesser-quality CCs should be improved. If we can boost productivity, we can reduce expenses and make more efficient use of our resources. Policymakers can utilize the results of efficiency estimates to identify inefficient facilities and implement reforms to increase their productivity. The results indicate that CCs may save a substantial amount of money by improving their operational efficiency.

Policymakers may find statistics on slacks and efficiency metrics valuable. Health authorities may find it useful to understand more about the technical efficiency of CCs and the variables that influence it. This might help them make better judgments and increase the technological efficiency of the CCs. If gaps exist, poor CCs may be able to increase productivity by reducing expenses and boosting production. Campaigns can increase demand, leading to an increase in output. If they increased the care and professionalism of their employees, more individuals could be interested in utilizing their services. CCs who do poorly may be able to instruct those who perform better. It is essential to assess ineffective CCs to see why they are not functioning as intended. A few things cannot be mentioned regarding the study's results. The DEA's results were founded on the premise that all inputs are utilized, and this should be emphasized first. Second, the tool requires a large number of DMUs to provide a decent output, however many facilities could not be added due to cost. Due of this, the program provides relative scores rather than absolute ones. In the study, just the most vital information was utilized. The third criterion for measuring efficiency is whether or not all resources are utilized effectively and the end product is satisfactory. The importance of quality-adjusted production in the healthcare industry is not included while assessing efficiency. In the health care sector, outcomes are impossible without increased output. However, there are still areas that require more investigation, especially since these issues must be resolved before the tools can be utilized effectively.

References

- Akazili, J., Adjuik, M., Jehu-Appiah, C., & Zere, E. (2008). Using data envelopment analysis to measure the extent of technical efficiency of public health centres in Ghana. *BMC international health and human rights*, 8, 1-12.
- Akono, C., Ndjokou, M. M., & Song-Ntamack, S. (2013). Institutions and Hospital Efficiency in Cameroon: A Data Envelope Analysis. *Journal of African Development*, 15(1), 45-71.
- Ahmed, S. N. (2009). Productivity modeling in the apparel industry of Bangladesh: an application of data envelopment analysis (DEA) technique.

- Ahn, H., & Le, M. H. (2014). An insight into the specification of the input-output set for DEA-based bank efficiency measurement. *Management Review Quarterly*, 64(1), 3-37.
- Athanassopoulos, A. D., & Ballantine, J. A. (1995). Ratio and frontier analysis for assessing corporate performance: evidence from the grocery industry in the UK. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 46(4), 427-440.
- Bahurmoz, A. M. (1999). Measuring efficiency in primary health care centres in Saudi Arabia. *Economics and Administration*, 12(2).
- Banker, R. D., Charnes, A., & Cooper, W. W. (1984). Some models for estimating technical and scale inefficiencies in data envelopment analysis. *Management science*, 30(9), 1078-1092.
- Banker, R. D., Cooper, W. W., Seiford, L. M., Thrall, R. M., & Zhu, J. (2004). Returns to scale in different DEA models. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 154(2), 345-362.
- Basso, A., & Funari, S. (2001). A data envelopment analysis approach to measure the mutual fund performance. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 135(3), 477-492.
- Bayyurt, N., & Yılmaz, S. (2012). The impacts of governance and education on agricultural efficiency: an international analysis. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 1158-1165.
- Buyukkeklik, A., Dumlu, H., & Evcı, S. (2016). Measuring the efficiency of turkish SMEs: A data envelopment analysis approach. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(6), 190-200.
- Caves, D. W., Christensen, L. R., & Diewert, W. E. (1982). The economic theory of index numbers and the measurement of input, output, and productivity. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 1393-1414.
- Charnes, A., & Cooper, W. W. (1979). *Management science relations for evaluation and management accountability*. Retrieved from
- Charnes, A., Cooper, W. W., & Rhodes, E. (1978). Measuring the efficiency of decision making units. *European journal of operational research*, 2(6), 429-444.
- Cheng, Z., Cai, M., Tao, H., He, Z., Lin, X., Lin, H., & Zuo, Y. (2016). Efficiency and productivity measurement of rural township hospitals in China: a bootstrapping data envelopment analysis. *BMJ open*, 6(11), e011911.
- Cooper, W. W., Seiford, L. M., & Tone, K. (2007). *Data envelopment analysis: a comprehensive text with models, applications, references and DEA-solver software* (Vol. 2): Springer.

- Din, M.-u., Ghani, E., & Mahmood, T. (2007). Technical efficiency of Pakistan's manufacturing sector: A stochastic frontier and data envelopment analysis. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 1-18.
- Düzakın, E., & Düzakın, H. (2007). Measuring the performance of manufacturing firms with super slacks based model of data envelopment analysis: An application of 500 major industrial enterprises in Turkey. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 182(3), 1412-1432.
- Emran, S. J., & Moniruzzaman, M. (2020). The Dynamics and Sources of Technical Efficiency of the Manufacturing Industries in Bangladesh.
- Farrell, M. The Measurement of Productive Efficiency *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General)*, 1957. In.
- Frija, A., Chebil, A., Speelman, S., Buysse, J., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2009). Water use and technical efficiencies in horticultural greenhouses in Tunisia. *Agricultural Water Management*, 96(11), 1509-1516.
- Gökgöz, F. (2010). Measuring the financial efficiencies and performances of Turkish funds. *Acta Oeconomica*, 60(3), 295-320.
- Henderson, J. M., & Quandt, R. E. (1971). *Microeconomic theory: A mathematical approach*. Retrieved from
- Hossen, M. A. (2014). Measuring gender-based violence: Results of the violence against women (VAW) survey in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), Ministry of Planning: Dhaka, Bangladesh*.
- Islam, A., & Biswas, T. (2014). Health system in Bangladesh: challenges and opportunities. *American Journal of Health Research*, 2(6), 366-374.
- Kirigia, J. M., Emrouznejad, A., Sambo, L. G., Munguti, N., & Liambila, W. (2004). Using data envelopment analysis to measure the technical efficiency of public health centers in Kenya. *Journal of medical systems*, 28, 155-166.
- Kassam, A. (2017). Efficiency analysis of healthcare sector. *Engineering and Technology Journal*, 35(5 Part A), 509-515.
- Khan, A. H., & Farooq, S. (2019). Evaluating Technical Efficiency of Textile Firms in Pakistan: An Application of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) Approach. *Paradigms*, 13(2), 160-169.
- Khan, M. F. Z. (2014). The Social and Financial Performance of Conventional and Islamic Microfinance Institutions in Pakistan. *Al-Idah*, 28(1), 17-34.
- Khan, M. M. N., Ahmad, A., & Jehan, N. (2018). Pakistani Firms' Efficiency: An Empirical Study of Pakistani Listed Firms through Data Envelopment Analysis. *Global Social Sciences Review (GSSR)*, 3, 158-174.

- Li, L., Li, M., & Wu, C. (2013). Production efficiency evaluation of energy companies based on the improved super-efficiency data envelopment analysis considering undesirable outputs. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 58(5-6), 1057-1067.
- Mogha, S. K., Yadav, S. P., & Singh, S. P. (2014). New slack model based efficiency assessment of public sector hospitals of Uttarakhand: State of India. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, 5(1), 32-42.
- Marschall, P., & Flessa, S. (2011). Efficiency of primary care in rural Burkina Faso. A two-stage DEA analysis. *Health economics review*, 1(1), 1-15.
- Organization, W. H. (2010). *World health statistics 2010*: World Health Organization.
- Osei, D., d'Almeida, S., George, M. O., Kirigia, J. M., Mensah, A. O., & Kainyu, L. H. (2005). Technical efficiency of public district hospitals and health centres in Ghana: a pilot study. *Cost effectiveness and resource allocation*, 3(1), 1-13.
- Osmani, A. R. (2012). Technical Efficiency of District Hospitals in Afghanistan: a Data Envelopment Analysis Approach. *PSAKU International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 1(1), 82-107.
- Ramanathan, R. (2003). *An introduction to data envelopment analysis: a tool for performance measurement*: Sage.
- Shetty, U., & Pakkala, T. (2010). Technical efficiencies of healthcare system in major states of India: an application of NP-RDM of DEA formulation. *Journal of Health Management*, 12(4), 501-518.
- Ahmed, S. N. (2009). Productivity modeling in the apparel industry of Bangladesh: an application of data envelopment analysis (DEA) technique.
- Ahn, H., & Le, M. H. (2014). An insight into the specification of the input-output set for DEA-based bank efficiency measurement. *Management Review Quarterly*, 64(1), 3-37.
- Athanassopoulos, A. D., & Ballantine, J. A. (1995). Ratio and frontier analysis for assessing corporate performance: evidence from the grocery industry in the UK. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 46(4), 427-440.
- Banker, R. D., Charnes, A., & Cooper, W. W. (1984). Some models for estimating technical and scale inefficiencies in data envelopment analysis. *Management science*, 30(9), 1078-1092.
- Banker, R. D., Cooper, W. W., Seiford, L. M., Thrall, R. M., & Zhu, J. (2004). Returns to scale in different DEA models. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 154(2), 345-362.

- Basso, A., & Funari, S. (2001). A data envelopment analysis approach to measure the mutual fund performance. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 135(3), 477-492.
- Bayyurt, N., & Yılmaz, S. (2012). The impacts of governance and education on agricultural efficiency: an international analysis. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 1158-1165.
- Buyukkeklik, A., Dumlu, H., & Evci, S. (2016). Measuring the efficiency of turkish SMEs: A data envelopment analysis approach. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(6), 190-200.
- Carrillo, M., & Jorge, J. M. (2017). DEA-like efficiency ranking of regional health systems in Spain. *Social Indicators Research*, 133(3), 1133-1149.
- Charnes, A., Cooper, W. W., & Rhodes, E. (1981). Evaluating program and managerial efficiency: an application of data envelopment analysis to program follow through. *Management science*, 27(6), 668-697.
- Cook, P. (2001). Finance and small and medium-sized enterprise in developing countries. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 6(1), 17.
- Din, M.-u., Ghani, E., & Mahmood, T. (2007). Technical efficiency of Pakistan's manufacturing sector: A stochastic frontier and data envelopment analysis. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 1-18.
- Düzakın, E., & Düzakın, H. (2007). Measuring the performance of manufacturing firms with super slacks based model of data envelopment analysis: An application of 500 major industrial enterprises in Turkey. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 182(3), 1412-1432.
- Emran, S. J., & Moniruzzaman, M. (2020). The Dynamics and Sources of Technical Efficiency of the Manufacturing Industries in Bangladesh.
- Farrell, M. The Measurement of Productive Efficiency *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General)*, 1957. In.
- Frija, A., Chebil, A., Speelman, S., Buysse, J., & Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2009). Water use and technical efficiencies in horticultural greenhouses in Tunisia. *Agricultural Water Management*, 96(11), 1509-1516.
- Gökgöz, F. (2010). Measuring the financial efficiencies and performances of Turkish funds. *Acta Oeconomica*, 60(3), 295-320.
- Index, E. (2010). Finance division, Ministry of Finance, Government of the People Republic of Bangladesh. In.
- Kassam, A. (2017). Efficiency analysis of healthcare sector. *Engineering and Technology Journal*, 35(5 Part A), 509-515.

- Khan, A. H., & Farooq, S. (2019). Evaluating Technical Efficiency of Textile Firms in Pakistan: An Application of Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) Approach. *Paradigms*, 13(2), 160-169.
- Khan, M. F. Z. (2014). The Social and Financial Performance of Conventional and Islamic Microfinance Institutions in Pakistan. *Al-Idah*, 28(1), 17-34.
- Khan, M. M. N., Ahmad, A., & Jehan, N. (2018). Pakistani Firms' Efficiency: An Empirical Study of Pakistani Listed Firms through Data Envelopment Analysis. *Global Social Sciences Review (GSSR)*, 3, 158-174.
- Li, L., Li, M., & Wu, C. (2013). Production efficiency evaluation of energy companies based on the improved super-efficiency data envelopment analysis considering undesirable outputs. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 58(5-6), 1057-1067.
- Mogha, S. K., Yadav, S. P., & Singh, S. P. (2014). New slack model based efficiency assessment of public sector hospitals of Uttarakhand: State of India. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, 5(1), 32-42.
- Njikam, O. (2003). Trade reform and efficiency in Cameroon's manufacturing industries: AERC.
- Pille, P., & Paradi, J. C. (2002). Financial performance analysis of Ontario (Canada) Credit Unions: An application of DEA in the regulatory environment. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 139(2), 339-350.
- Raheli, H., Rezaei, R. M., Jadidi, M. R., & Mobtaker, H. G. (2017). A two-stage DEA model to evaluate sustainability and energy efficiency of tomato production. *Information Processing in Agriculture*, 4(4), 342-350.
- Si, L.-B., & Qiao, H.-Y. (2017). Performance of Financial Expenditure in China's basic science and math education: Panel Data Analysis Based on CCR Model and BBC Model. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 13(8), 5217-5224.
- Staub, R. B., e Souza, G. d. S., & Tabak, B. M. (2010). Evolution of bank efficiency in Brazil: A DEA approach. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 202(1), 204-213.
- Taymaz, E., & Saatci, G. (1997). Technical change and efficiency in Turkish manufacturing industries. *Journal of Productivity Analysis*, 8(4), 461-475.
- Thanassoulis, E. (2001). *Introduction to the theory and application of data envelopment analysis*: Springer.
- Titko, J., Stankevičienė, J., & Lāce, N. (2014). Measuring bank efficiency: DEA application. *Technological and economic development of economy*, 20(4), 739-757.

Tone, K. (2001). A slacks-based measure of efficiency in data envelopment analysis. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 130(3), 498-509.

Wang, Y., Pan, J.-f., Pei, R.-m., Yi, B.-W., & Yang, G.-l. (2020). Assessing the technological innovation efficiency of China's high-tech industries with a two-stage network DEA approach. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 71, 100810.

Wei, C.-K., Chen, L.-C., Li, R.-K., & Tsai, C.-H. (2011). Exploration of efficiency underestimation of CCR model: Based on medical sectors with DEA-R model. *Expert systems with applications*, 38(4), 3155-3160.

Yadava, A. K., & Komaraiah, J. B. (2021). Benchmarking the performance of organic farming in India. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 21(2), e2208.

Zere, E., Mbeeli, T., Shangula, K., Mandlhate, C., Mutirua, K., Tjivambi, B., & Kapenambili, W. (2006). Technical efficiency of district hospitals: evidence from Namibia using data envelopment analysis. *Cost effectiveness and resource allocation*, 4(1), 1-9.

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2023 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Easmin, N., & Hurira, A. (2023). Technical Efficiency of Community Clinics in Kushtia, Bangladesh: A Nonparametric DEA Analysis. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 10 (5), 339-359.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8062689</p> <p>DOR: 20.1001.1.23832126.2023.10.5.3.4</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_173054.html</p>	